

Managerial support's moderating role in Indonesian lecturers' career insight

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ABSTRACT

Lecturers' academic careers as professional workers have a different process from other workers. Understanding career insights is important for lecturers in carrying out their profession. this research aims to test the moderating effect of managerial support on the influence of career motivation and self-concept on career insight. this research uses quantitative methods, data collection uses instruments with a 1-5 Likert scale. Respondents were 499 lecturers in Jakarta, Indonesia. The data analysis technique uses SEM PLS. The research results show that career motivation and self concept have a positive effect on lecturers' career insight. meanwhile, managerial support does not have a significant moderating effect on the influence of career motivation and self concept on career insight. this research recommends the need for efforts to increase the role of managerial support in increasing lecturers' career insight. this is an opportunity for further research with different theoretical and methodological aspects.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The examination of career alternatives and choices has become more complex in the twenty-first century due to changes in the world of work [1], [2]. Prior research in the field of careers has predominantly examined the subject of career advancement and the attainment of career success, encompassing both subjective and objective measures. These measures include the accomplishment of personal objectives and the acquisition of concrete rewards, such as promotions, across diverse professional domains [3]–[5]. In contrast to the focus that was placed on other elements, the present emphasis in career development is placed more heavily on the ways in which individual and contextual factors impact changes that occur in a person's profession throughout the course of their working life [5], [6]. Career has now become a series that is difficult to predict [7]. Career theory, in general, has been criticized for placing too much emphasis on the individual and ignoring contextual issues that organizations need [8]. The study of careers is still wide open in various perspectives such as, physiological correlation of career motivation, cognitive correlation of career motivation or various career problems in special populations [9]–[11].

Lecturers, as a population of professional workers, of course have various demands like other workers [12]. Professional identity is defined as an individual's perception of oneself as a professional in a professional community. The career of a lecturer is a complex and challenging professional journey [13]. In the case of Indonesia as a study locus, the number of Indonesian lecturers will reach 311,642 people in 2021. If you look at campus status, as many as 82,608 lecturers teach at state universities. Meanwhile, there are 182,844 lecturers at private universities. The highest career achievement for lecturers is becoming a professor [14]. According to the 2021 Higher Education Statistics in Indonesia, a mere 7,192 individuals, about 2.25 percent of the total 320,052 lecturers in the country, were bestowed with the esteemed designation of professor. The current number of professors in Indonesia falls far below the recommended threshold, which suggests that 10 percent of the total lecturers should hold this esteemed academic rank, or it is expected that each study program should have at least one professor [15]. The reasons for the low number of professors in Indonesia is that lecturers are less concerned about understanding the requirements needed to advance their careers in positions or higher ranks, including achieving the level of professor [16].

Understanding the academic career of a lecturer has a different process from other workers. Academic career development encompasses the dynamic interaction between employers and lecturers in effectively managing diverse duties, behaviors, and experiences within and across positions and organizations over an extended period [5]. The task as a lecturer is to teach and focus on research, which in the end can contribute to society according to their field of expertise [17]. There are several main problems that lecturers may face. Some of these include: difficulty finding funding sources for research projects; Competition in the world of academic research is very tight. The work demands of lecturers are so complicated, such as allocating time between teaching demands, administrative duties, and other responsibilities as a lecturer; Book publishing and Publications; access to facilities and infrastructure; and carrying out various collaborative activities to develop networks [10], [13], [18].

Lecturer career problems cannot be overcome only by individual lecturers, but require institutional support, a supportive career development system and of course superiors or faculty leaders who should be able to provide effective supervision and managerial support [11], [19]. Lecturers as individuals and faculty managers need to align their respective interests [20], [21], it is necessary to align interests between individual careers and organizational interests. Career insight is absolutely understood by lecturers [22]. Career insight can be defined as the individual's realistic picture of themselves, their company, and their career ambitions. Career identity is also a component of career insight. The degree to which individuals remain current with innovations in their field of expertise and consider themselves to be professionals [9].

The working relationship between lecturers and faculty leadership officials who usually have lecturer status, is often a collegial relationship, mutual respect and there is a reluctance to encourage the careers of other lecturers, even though hierarchically lecturers are functional staff of the faculty under the responsibility of the dean [23]. In practice, lecturers' careers are often determined by their own initiative, while the institution is only a passive facilitator. Even though there are many challenges in a lecturer's career, it is still possible for lecturers to achieve success in the academic world [24], [25]. In facing existing challenges, lecturers need to have a deep understanding of the career path they choose and how to manage their career development [26]. What is the role of faculty leaders in encouraging lecturers towards career insight in order to achieve career success [27], [28]. Faculty leaders must understand individual lecturers in their environment regarding aspects of individual needs, organizational demands, and individual career goals; as well as the extent to which individuals undergo their professional development.

Over the past decade, the nature of job shifts and career patterns that involve a variety of transitions have both been the subject of studies in the academic literature [29], [30]. This is because there are changes in the roles of workers, managers, jobs, economic conditions, and even personal interests [31], [32]. Previous research shows that self-exploration and the work environment are important for making career choices [33], including for lecturers. This research seeks to complete the existing research gap, where previous research focused more on the company scope and this research seeks to examine the role of managerial support (faculty leaders) as an organizational representative in moderating lecturers' career insight. This research certainly contributes to the literature on career management [6], [13], [26], [34] especially in terms of career development for lecturers at universities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Career insight

Higher education has undergone a major transformation in the last decade. The campus ecosystem requires lecturers to develop their academic careers. Lecturers must focus on increasing their competence their expertise, while being able to contribute significantly to knowledge, and be able to build collaborative relationships with fellow academics nationally and internationally, which in the end can contribute significantly

to society [26]. For lecturers, academic career development is an individual process. Lecturers must be able to adapt to their main duties of carrying out teaching, research and community service [6], [13], [26], [34]. construction career theory (CCT), proposed by Savickas [35], describes an individual's ability to adapt in a career. About the individual's readiness to cope with predictable tasks. Individuals must also be able to prepare for and participate in their work roles and adjust to the unpredictability of changes in their jobs and working conditions. The career perspective in practice shows that there is an interdependence between individual career development, career opportunities and career development provided by the organization [36], [37]. Previous studies show that alignment of individual career interests with people and organizations results in positive outcomes in career success [38].

Career is assumed to play an important role in maintaining employee value to the organization [39]. The development of lecturers' academic careers through the process of carrying out teaching, research and community service where the development of lecturers' academic careers is different from academic careers in general [24], [40]. In this research, the focus is on individual lecturer and contextual factors that can contribute to changes in lecturers' career paths. Zacher *et al.* [5] in their study found that academic career development is very important and must be timely because working in the academic world is a unique career path for individuals according to their field of study. Understanding careers for lecturers is very necessary. Lecturers as professional workers with relatively high levels of education, have autonomy in carrying out their work, such as teaching and research [16]. Based on a broad career conceptualization, career insight refers to an individual's realistic perception of their own self, the organization they are a part of, and their career objectives. On the other hand, career identity pertains to the degree to which individuals actively engage with advancements in their chosen profession and perceive themselves as professionals [9].

2.2. Career motivation and career insight

Motivation is a definition of why individuals behave the way they do, what triggers behavior, what directs, energizes, maintains and performs it [41]. Motivation is very important for almost all aspects of life, especially in working and achieving a career. There are few humans who do not question or reflect on their motivation for certain tasks every day [42]. Career motivation (CM), guides individual career decisions and behavior [22]. Individual aptitudes and motivation, working conditions, organizational interventions, and policy approaches are necessary for the practice of a person's professional journey [12]. Apart from individual behavior in choosing work, and the process of completing work, which includes career decision making, self-efficacy, and career maturity [43], [44]. Career motivation influences individuals' conceptions of their careers [45]. In detail, career motivation as an Individual Characteristics Domain [22], in motivational terms, is a component that gives energy, identity, sets goals. Goals include clarity of path goals and clarity of means to achieve career goals as well as flexibility of goals, changes in interest in new and different career experiences. Self-objectivity in assessing one's strengths, weaknesses and motives. Realistic expectations about career outcomes, for example, progress, salary, career and future. Various previous literature also supports this argument, namely that career motivation can influence an individual's career insight [12], [46], [47]. Based on this description, the first hypothesis is formulated, namely:

H1: CM has a positive effect on career insight (CI)

2.3. Self-concept and career insight

Self concept (SC), is an aspect of knowledge about oneself, the extent to which an individual's concept is clearly defined, such as self-confidence, consistency and stability over time [48]–[50]. Self-concept can be described as a concept that reflects confidence and consistency regardless of the content or accuracy of the self-concept itself [51]. Self-concept is included in the self-confidence group [52], self-concept also refers to a person's perception of and assessment of their own abilities [53]. Self-concept in general is a person's perception of himself. This self-perception can be determined and shaped by a person's interaction with the interpretation of their environment [49], [54]. Some general opinions say that being a lecturer is a profession of choice that is a calling. Lecturer is a professional choice and a self-concept in choosing a job, namely attitudes and values as job-related needs. Developing a robust self-concept pertaining to the work environment aids instructors in cultivating more pragmatic expectations for their professional roles [55], [56]. Lecturers who have a good Self Concept towards their profession will be more confident and have good career insight [7], [31], [34], [45]. Based on this description, the second hypothesis in this research is as follows.

H2: SC has a positive effect on career insight (CI)

2.4. Managerial support as moderator

In the campus world, this topic is directed at the chief academic officer (CAO) with the hope of being able to play a role in the effective management process and efficient operations of higher education [57], [58]. Academic management is an ambiguous and very intuitive process, requiring improvisation on managerial behavior, which can provide managerial support in various matters, especially in lecturer career development

[59]–[61]. Previous research results found that leaders, with their various functions, have a role in the career success of their subordinates [11], [46]. Individuals with successful careers tend to have good levels of manager support [9]. Career motivation is significantly elevated when individuals receive assistance from their supervisors, who offer explicit performance comments and actively promote the establishment of career objectives by subordinates. London [22] explained that one aspect of career motivation is the desire to move upward. Individuals will set a career path for their possible career advancement, and hope to be promoted. A manager, should provide clear performance feedback, provide career insight and encourage subordinates to set career goals. Leaders must function like mentors and demonstrate a high level of career motivation. Employees who receive good mentoring will encourage greater career motivation [62]. Likewise, self-concept, which describes an individual's mental representation and evaluation of competence [50], [63], is difficult to be actualized in driving a career without the support of leadership. Various literature states that the concepts of Career Motivation and Self Concept cannot be actualized to influence career insight, without managerial support [64]–[66]. Based on this explanation, the third and fourth hypotheses were formulated.

H3: Managerial support (MS) moderates self-concept (SC) on career insight (CI)

H4: Managerial support (MS) moderates career motivation (CM) on career insight (CI)

3. METHOD

3.1. Research design

This research uses a quantitative approach with SEM to analyze the role of managerial support in moderating the influence of Self Concept and Career Motivation on Career Insight Figure 1. A quantitative approach allows for more measurable measurements and in-depth statistical analysis of the relationship between the variables studied. SEM analysis allows researchers to understand holistically how these variables interact with each other and contribute to an understanding of a person's career insight.

Figure 1. The proposed research models

3.2. Participants and Data Collection

Researchers have conducted surveys on populations through samples to describe attitudes, opinions, behavior or characteristics of the population. We randomly distributed questionnaires to lecturers from various universities in Jakarta as participants. The sample was taken based on convenience sampling, based on Nunnally [67] recommendation, the appropriate sample size should be above or close to 300 to prevent bias and error. Therefore, a questionnaire using Google form was sent to 600 lecturers via WhatsApp, in May-July 2023. Anonymity was granted to the participants in the study, who willingly responded to the questionnaire items. A total of 499 responses were collected, resulting in a response rate of 83.1%. In addition to the aforementioned point, it is important to note that Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Indonesia, has obtained ethical clearance.

The questionnaire uses a Likert scale to assess the attitudes, views, and perceptions of individuals or groups on social phenomena. The instrument for each variable adapts the previous instrument. Managerial support, adapted from Holt *et al.* [68] consists of 6 items; Career insight adapted from Day and Allen [62] 7 items; Self-Concept, instrument adapted from Goñi *et al.* [69] 10 items; Career motivation adapted from Mayer *et al.* [70] 10 items. The translation of all instruments was conducted into the Indonesian language, as the

participants of the study were Indonesian lecturers. The accuracy of the translation was ensured by the process of back translation. The instruments underwent rigorous testing through the utilization of expert judgment to ascertain the alignment of the statements with the study objectives.

3.3. Data Analysis

The analysis methodology employed in this study adhered to the standards outlined by Hair *et al.* [71], encompassing the evaluation of the outer model measurement, inner model measurement, and hypothesis testing. The outer measurement model comprises three key components: convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability. Convergent validity is established when the average variance extracted (AVE) exceeds 0.5. Discriminant validity is achieved when the diagonal elements of the correlation matrix are greater than 0.7. Lastly, composite reliability is deemed satisfactory when it surpasses 0.7. The data analysis procedure employs the utilization of partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) with Smart-PLS version 3.0.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. outer model assesment

Table 1 displays the composite reliability (CR) values for each construct, which range from 0.842 to 0.966. These values surpass the threshold of 0.7, which is the established criterion for establishing adequate CR [71]. In addition, Table 2 presents the discriminant computations, employing the Fornell-Larcker criterion as a means to assess discriminant validity. The cross-loading has a smaller magnitude in comparison to the loading on the latent construct. This finding demonstrates that the variables exhibit a satisfactory level of discriminant validity.

Table 1. Construct reliability and validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	CR	AVE
CI	0.853	0.867	0.895	0.632
MS	0.958	0.962	0.966	0.825
CM	0.870	0.884	0.902	0.608
SC	0.718	0.724	0.842	0.642

Table 2. Discriminant validity (fornell-larcker criterion)

	CI	MS	CM	SC
CI	0.795			
MS	0.388	0.908		
CM	0.617	0.367	0.780	
SC	0.529	0.271	0.570	0.801

Referring to Table 3 collinearity statistics (VIF), it shows that there is no multiple collinearities. The results of the Goodness of Fit (GoF) test are presented in Table 4. The Standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) value is found to be less than 0.063, indicating that the model can be deemed appropriate or fitting. The normal fit index (NFI) value ranges from 0 to 1. According to the criteria by Hu and Bentler [72], a higher value closer to 1 indicates better performance. The standardized SRMR value is 0.063. The result in question is below 0.08, so indicating that the model is deemed suitable. In addition, the NFI value of 0.857, which is in proximity to 1, indicates that the model can be deemed appropriate.

Table 3. Collinearity statistics (VIF)

Career insight	
Career insight	
Managerial Support	1.170
Career Motivation	2.036
Self Concept	1.623

Table 4. Model Fit

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.063	0.063
d_ ULS	0.844	0.846
d_ G	0.347	0.347
Chi-Square	808.757	809.303
NFI	0.857	0.857

4.2. Inner model assesment

The findings from the outer model demonstrate satisfactory results, thus warranting additional research. Hence, the subsequent phase in partial least squares (PLS) analysis involves constructing an internal model that facilitates the evaluation of the interrelationships among various constructs. The subsequent step in the inner model involves doing the r-squared (R^2) test, which serves the purpose of assessing the degree of accuracy or imprecision in the predictions made by the endogenous latent variables identified within the model. The R^2 value is employed as a benchmark to assess the predictive capability and precision of endogenous variables within the model, as stated by Hair *et al.* [71]. Based on the calculated R^2 value (refer to Table 5), the variable representing career insight demonstrates a coefficient of 0.454. This indicates that approximately 45.4 percent of the variability in career insight can be accounted for by the variables MS, CM, and SC, with a moderate level of predictive accuracy. The subsequent step involves the estimation of the effect magnitude (f^2). In this study, the threshold value of f^2 is determined based on suggestions provided by Hair *et al.* [71]. The estimation findings for f^2 , as presented in Table 6, indicate that MS and SC exert a statistically significant influence on CI at a significance level below 0.15. Additionally, CM demonstrates a moderate effect on CI, with an estimated coefficient falling between the range of 0.15 to 0.35. Consequently, we can infer that the model possesses predictive relevance.

Table 5. R square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Career insight	0.454	0.447

Table 6. F square

Career insight	
CI	
MS	0.046
CM	0.155
SC	0.073

All data were run using 499 bootstrap samples. The findings pertaining to the inner model testing are presented in Table 7. The results provide support for two hypotheses ($p < 0.05$) while two hypotheses were found to be rejected ($p > 0.05$). A hypothesis test's findings in Table 7 show that Career Motivation has a significant positive effect on Career insight, ($p = 0.000$), which means that increasing motive will increase lecturers' career insight. These results indicate that H1 is accepted. Self Concept has a positive and significant effect on Career insight, ($p = 0.000$), so H2 is accepted. Meanwhile, Managerial support cannot be proven to moderate the relationship between Career Motivation and Career insight, nor is Managerial support proven to moderate Self Concept towards Career insight.

Table 7. Hypothesis testing using PLS

Path	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
MS mod CM-CI -> CI	-0.004	0.061	0.058	0.954	Rejected
MS mod SC-CI -> CI	0.034	0.057	0.600	0.549	Rejected
CM -> CI	0.415	0.068	6.141	0.000	Accepted
SC -> CI	0.254	0.057	4.470	0.000	Accepted

4.3. Discussion

Based on the four hypotheses proposed, the results of this study show that we have accepted the hypothesis that Career motivation has a positive effect on Career insight. This strengthens previous research [12], [46], [47]. Motivation as a reason for action is something important in encouraging lecturers' career paths in their work [41], [42]. The higher the career motivation, the more career insight will increase and in turn this will encourage career acceleration and will help facilitate career development patterns. Results of testing the relationship between career motivation and career insight in the context of individuals who are developing their careers. These results support the assumption that strong motivation in developing a career can have a positive impact on individuals' understanding of career opportunities and goals [9], [10], [62], [70]. In this context, lecturers with a higher level of career motivation tend to be active in seeking information about development trends in the world of education, developing career opportunities, and the requirements needed to achieve the desired career.

In this research, it has been clearly revealed that there is a significant and positive relationship between self-concept and career insight. These findings provide a deeper understanding of how lecturers' self-perceptions influence the way lecturers understand career opportunities and future goals. This research makes a valuable contribution to understanding the psychological dynamics involved in individual career development. Self-concept, as a central concept in individual psychology, has a fundamental role in shaping perceptions and actions [48], [73]. The results of this research indicate that lecturers with a positive self-concept tend to have a more optimistic view and self-confidence about their abilities. The positive self-concept that lecturers have in turn encourages lecturers to carry out deeper exploration of career fields that interest lecturers. Career insight, which includes an understanding of career opportunities and goals, seems to have to be built on a strong self-concept foundation [7], [31], [34], [45]. Individuals with a clear view of their personal values, interests, and potential are more likely to identify career fields that are appropriate or that have a better fit with their goals [31], [53]. Moreover, they may also be more open to learning from experiences and challenges in career development.

Research findings also show that managerial support does not have a significant moderating effect between career motivation and career insight. These findings indicate that although managerial support has important value in the context of work environment, it does not significantly moderate the relationship between career motivation and career insight [9], [65]. This means that the effect of career motivation on career insight remains relatively consistent, regardless of the level of managerial support received by the individual. Although managerial support can provide emotional, informational, or training support that can influence career development [74], it does not appear to change the fundamental relationship between individuals' motivation and their understanding of career opportunities.

As other findings show, managerial support does not have a significant moderating effect in this relationship. Discussion of these findings provides insight into how the role of managerial support may not influence the relationship between self-concept and career insight. Individuals with a positive self-concept may tend to be more confident in taking steps that support their career development [45], [46]. By having a clear view of personal values, interests, and potential, such individuals may be more inclined to plan and make decisions that align with their career goals [48], [53], [73].

5. CONCLUSION

The very important thing in this research shows that there is no influence of the role of managerial support in increasing lecturers' career insight, for this reason chief academic officers need to better understand the career motivation and self-concept of lecturers and individual understanding of their career opportunities and goals. Practical implications in developing lecturers' careers, at universities, there is a need to consider ways to motivate and facilitate lecturers more effectively and encourage lecturers to better understand their career insights. Increasing lecturer careers will improve the university's reputation, for this reason it is important to increase the role of Managerial support in improving lecturer careers. Campus institutions must be able to design programs that strengthen the positive self-concept of lecturers. Identifying and establishing personal values and interests can assist individuals in planning a more suitable career. Apart from that, it is necessary to motivate lecturers to dare to act to achieve these goals. It is time for lecturers as career professionals to be more proactive in developing their own careers. This research has limitations, such as limitations in the methods or measurements used. We recommend that further research be carried out to deepen understanding of the role of managerial support in lecturers' careers by digging deeper into other factors that might influence the relationship between career motivation, self-concept and career insight.

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